

Description of EERIE idealised atmosphere-only simulations

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Executive Summary

This report describes a multi-model dataset of idealised atmosphere-only sensitivity experiments, which are designed to complement EERIE reference simulations and help disentangle the impacts of the ocean mesoscale on weather and climate variability. The purpose of these experiments is to evaluate the response of the atmospheric circulation to the direct thermodynamic forcing attributable to extratropical SST anomalies associated with quasi-stationary fronts or transient mesoscale features (e.g. nonlinear eddies). These experiments are conducted with two resolutions of the IFS (~28 km and ~9 km) and HadGEM3 (~60 km and ~20 km) atmosphere models. Ocean and sea-ice boundary conditions are derived from high-resolution satellite-based estimates of daily-mean sea surface temperatures (SST) and sea-ice concentration from the European Space Agency Sea Surface Temperature Climate Change Initiative (ESA CCI SST version 3.0) and the European Organisation for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites (EUMETSAT) Ocean and Sea Ice Satellite Application Facility (OSI-SAF), respectively. Other than the specification of SST boundary conditions, the idealised simulations described here are identical to the EERIE atmosphere-only reference experiments described in EERIE Deliverable 9.3. In these idealised experiments, extratropical SSTs are modified with a physically-informed spatial filter to suppress the influence of either transient mesoscale anomalies (*SmoothAnom* experiments) or sharp gradients associated with ocean fronts (*SmoothClim* experiments). A preliminary evaluation of these idealised experiments indicates that transient mesoscale SST anomalies can have a small but systematic impact on the climatological zonal winds and position of the tropospheric jets. However, the vertical and latitudinal structure of the zonal wind response to ocean eddies varies by season, hemisphere, and model configuration. Future work will assess the statistical robustness of these preliminary results and work towards understanding the physical mechanisms associated with the large-scale atmospheric response to transient mesoscale SST anomalies and quasi-stationary fronts in the EERIE simulations.

1 Introduction

One of the principal objectives of the EERIE project is to improve our understanding of the local and remote atmospheric response to ocean mesoscale features, including quasi-stationary fronts, nonlinear ocean eddies, and other meandering and/or filamentary structures that scale with the first baroclinic Rossby radius of deformation (L_R). The value of L_R represents the length scale at which rotational and buoyancy effects become comparable for the development of flow disturbances and thus sets the typical spatial scale for baroclinic instability. In the ocean, this length scale varies with latitude, vertical stratification, and bathymetry such that $L_R > 500$ km close to the equator and $L_R < 5$ km in coastal regions near the poles (Hallberg, 2013).

Variations in ocean temperature, salinity, and velocity associated with ocean mesoscale processes can influence the atmosphere via a range of *direct* and *indirect* mechanisms. For example, spatial variations in sea surface temperature (SST) associated with ocean fronts and eddies can modulate turbulent fluxes of sensible and latent heat that directly modify the temperature, humidity, stability, and near-surface winds (Chelton et al. 2004; Xie, 2004; Chelton and Xie, 2010; Minobe et al. 2008; Small et al. 2008; Minobe et al. 2010) in the local marine atmospheric boundary layer (MABL). Similarly, variations in ocean surface currents associated with mesoscale features have been shown to modulate surface momentum fluxes that modify the magnitude and vorticity of near-surface winds (Renault et al. 2017; Renault et al. 2019). Recent work has also emphasized the important role for convergence and vertical motions associated with atmospheric fronts in communicating these impacts on the MABL into the upper troposphere (Parfitt and Czaja, 2016; O'Neill et al. 2017; Sheldon et al., 2017; Vanniere et al. 2017; Parfitt and Seo, 2018; Chakravorty et al. 2024; Christ et al. 2024). On longer timescales, mesoscale eddies modulate ocean heat and salinity budgets and thus indirectly influence air-sea interactions through large-scale changes in the ocean mean state and variability (Kirtman et al. 2012; Griffies et al. 2015; Roberts et al. 2019; Hewitt et al. 2020).

For an in-depth discussion of ocean mesoscale air-sea interactions and their influence on the large-scale atmospheric circulation, we refer the interested reader to the recent review paper by Seo et al. (2023). This review emphasises that there have been many advances in our understanding of mesoscale air-sea interactions during the last two decades. In particular, the impact of mesoscale SST anomalies on the local MABL is now well-established (e.g. Xie 2004; Small et al. 2008; Frenger et al. 2013; Chelton et al. 2004). There is also emerging evidence from idealised studies that mesoscale SST anomalies can modify the large-scale atmospheric circulation and associated precipitation patterns (e.g. Ma et al. 2015; Piazza et al. 2016; Ma et al. 2017; Foussard et al. 2019; Liu et al. 2021). However, the relative importance of sharp SST gradients associated with ocean fronts and transient ocean eddies on the large-scale extratropical

atmospheric circulation remains uncertain. Seo et al. (2023) emphasize the importance of coordinated high-resolution experimentation and common diagnostics to advance understanding in this area.

Idealised experiment	Atmosphere model	Horizontal resolution	Ensemble size	Period	Status
SmoothAnom	IFS	Tco1279 (~9 km)	1 member	1980-2023	Complete
	IFS	Tco399 (~28 km)	5 members		Complete
	UM	N640 (~20 km)	1 member	1980-2023	2014
	UM	N216 (~60 km)	1 member		Complete
SmoothClim	IFS	Tco399 (~28 km)	5 members	1980-2023	Complete

Table 1: Summary of idealised atmosphere-only simulations.

This report describes a multi-model dataset of idealised global atmosphere-only sensitivity experiments, which are designed to complement the eddy-rich EERIE coupled simulations (deliverable 4.1; Roberts, M.J. et al. 2024) and help disentangle the *direct* and *indirect* impacts of the ocean mesoscale on weather and climate variability. In particular, we discuss the following experiments:

- **Reference:** EERIE atmosphere-only reference simulations with ocean and sea-ice boundary conditions specified using high-resolution satellite-based estimates of daily-mean sea surface temperatures (SST) and sea-ice concentration from the European Space Agency Sea Surface Temperature Climate Change Initiative (ESA CCI SST version 3.0) and the European Organisation for the Exploitation of Meteorological Satellites (EUMETSAT) Ocean and Sea Ice Satellite Application Facility (OSI-SAF), respectively. These experiments are described in EERIE deliverable 9.3. (Roberts, C.D. et al. 2024).
- **SmoothAnom:** As *Reference*, but daily-mean SST boundary conditions are modified to suppress transient mesoscale SST anomalies in the extratropics. Climatological SSTs are not changed.
- **SmoothClim:** As *Reference*, but daily-mean SST boundary conditions are modified to smooth out sharp SST gradients associated with climatological ocean fronts in the extratropics. SST anomalies are not changed.

The purpose of these experiments is to evaluate the response of the global atmospheric circulation (in the absence of ocean feedbacks) to the *direct* thermodynamic forcing attributable to extratropical SST anomalies associated with quasi-stationary fronts (*SmoothClim*) and transient mesoscale features (*SmoothAnom*). These experiments are conducted with two resolutions of the IFS (~28 km and ~9 km) and HadGEM3 (~60 km and ~20 km) atmosphere models (see table 1). Other than the specification of SST boundary conditions, the idealised simulations described here are identical to the EERIE atmosphere-only reference experiments described in deliverable 9.3 (Roberts, C.D. et al. 2024).

The remainder of this report is organised as follows: Section 2 describes the IFS and HadGEM3 atmosphere-only model configurations. Section 3 describes the idealised SST boundary conditions, including the construction of climatologies, calculation of anomalies, and spatial filtering methods. Section 4 describes the data produced by each model and its availability to EERIE project partners. Section 5 provides a preliminary evaluation of the impact of transient mesoscale eddies on the atmospheric mean state by comparing *SmoothAnom* and *Reference* simulations.

2 Atmosphere models

The idealised simulations described in this report are produced using exactly the same versions of the ECMWF Integrated Forecasting System (IFS) and Met Office Unified Model (UM) that were used to produce the EERIE reference atmosphere-only simulations. The full details of each model configuration are available in EERIE deliverable 9.3 (Roberts, C.D. et al. 2024) and, for brevity, will not be repeated here. The only difference between the reference configurations and idealised experiments described here is the specification of SST boundary conditions. A comprehensive description of the processing of SST boundary conditions is provided in Section 3 below.

3 Idealised SST boundary conditions

Idealised SST boundary conditions are based on the European Space Agency Sea Surface Temperature Climate Change Initiative (ESA CCI SST version 3.0; Embury et al. 2024), which is the same dataset used for the EERIE reference atmosphere-only experiments described in deliverable 9.3 (Roberts, C.D. et al. 2024). Climatologies and anomalies are processed separately in order to construct boundary conditions appropriate for evaluating (1) the atmospheric response to

quasi-stationary fronts (*SmoothClim*) and (2) the atmospheric response to transient mesoscale features (*SmoothAnom*). Our procedure is comprised of the following steps:

1. Compute daily SST climatologies and associated daily anomalies (section 3.1).
2. Select and apply an appropriate “physically-informed” spatial filter separately to daily SST climatologies and daily SST anomalies (section 3.2).
3. Construct idealised SST boundary conditions from the appropriate combination of original/filtered SST climatologies and SST anomalies at each grid point (section 3.3).

All processing takes place on the grid ESA CCI SST is distributed on ($0.05^\circ \times 0.05^\circ$) and only the final idealised SST boundary condition is conservatively interpolated to the required model grid using the same approach as deliverable 9.3 (Roberts, C.D. et al. 2024).

3.1 Climatology definition

SST climatologies for the period 1991-2020 are defined separately for each day of the year and each ocean grid point. To minimise unphysical day-to-day variations in the resulting climatology we apply a tricube LOESS filter with a 20-day window to the 30-year time series at each grid point and then compute 9-day centered climatological means (± 4 days) for each day. This results in a smooth climatology with daily time resolution. The special case of February 29th is created as the mean of the values of February 28th and March 1st. Daily anomalies are then defined with respect to the daily climatology.

3.2 Spatial filter

Previous studies have evaluated the atmospheric response to strong SST gradients by directly smoothing SST boundary conditions with simple filters (e.g. running means) that do not discriminate between climatological and transient mesoscale SST features (e.g. Minobe et al. 2008). Here, we spatially filter climatologies and anomalies separately, which provides flexibility to generate boundary conditions that selectively isolate the SST features of interest. In addition, we use a “physically-informed” spatial filter with a cutoff length scale that varies with the local Rossby radius of deformation (L_{R_i}) and is thus appropriate for global fields. Specifically, we use a Gaussian filter as implemented in the [GCM-filters](#) Python package (Grooms et al. 2021; Loose et al. 2022) with the following desirable properties:

- Diffusion-based filtering based on a discrete Laplacian operator, which respects varying grid-cell geometry and no-flux boundary conditions (e.g. coastlines).
- Conserves global integrals.

- Supports spatially-varying filter length scales.
- Efficient filtering of high resolution datasets on GPUs.

We filter both SST climatologies and SST anomalies with the same spatially-varying length scale of $20 L_R$, which is derived from the Polar science center Hydrographic Climatology (PHC) climatology following Rackow et al. (2022). We specify upper and lower limits to the filter length scale of 30 km and 700 km, respectively, to focus the effects of our filter on the ocean fronts and mesoscale eddies that are typical of the mid-latitude open oceans.

3.3 Masking and combining SST fields

Despite using a length scale that varies with L_R , the filter described in Section 3.2 has some unwanted impacts on SSTs in the low latitudes due to large values of L_R associated with the small values of the Coriolis parameter, which approach zero close to the equator. In particular, there is a strong smoothing of Tropical Instability Waves (TIWs), which are not the focus of the EERIE project. Based on preliminary experimentation, it was evident that differences in tropical SST boundary conditions might confound interpretation of the response to extratropical SSTs due the influence of tropical-extratropical teleconnections. For this reason, we choose to suppress the impact of differences in the tropics by blending filtered and unfiltered data with a masking function (m) that varies with latitude (θ). The SST boundary conditions for each experiment are then derived as follows

$$m(\theta) = \frac{1}{2} \left(\tanh \left(\frac{|h - \theta|}{s} \right) + 1 \right)$$

$$\overline{\text{SST}}_{Reference} = \overline{\text{Climatology}} + \overline{\text{Anomaly}} = \overline{\text{SST}} + \overline{\text{SST}^*}$$

$$\text{SST}_{SmoothAnom} = \overline{\text{SST}} + \mathcal{G}(\overline{\text{SST}^*}) + m(\theta) [\overline{\text{SST}^*} - \mathcal{G}(\overline{\text{SST}^*})]$$

$$\text{SST}_{SmoothClim} = \overline{\text{SST}^*} + \mathcal{G}(\overline{\text{SST}}) + m(\theta) \left[\overline{\text{SST}} - \mathcal{G}(\overline{\text{SST}}) \right]$$

where G is a spatial smoothing operator, h is the half-power latitude of the masking function, s is the steepness of the masking function, and overbars and asterisks represent climatologies and anomalies, respectively. Locations with $m=1$ use the same SST boundary condition as *Reference* experiments. Locations with $m=0$ remove high-pass filtered features in climatologies or anomalies, depending on the experiment. We specify $h=10$ and $s=3$ such that TIWs are retained in our

idealised experiments while maintaining a smooth transition to the filtered regime in the extratropics (figure 1).

Figure 1: Impact of SST filtering on SST anomalies in the tropical Pacific region. (left) Original daily SST anomalies, (centre) low-pass filtered SST anomalies, and (right) high-pass filtered features reintroduced within approximately 10 degrees latitude of the equator.

3.4 SST in *SmoothAnom* and *SmoothClim*

The SST boundary conditions for reference and idealised experiments are illustrated for the Gulf Stream region in figure 2. Other regions are shown in figures A1, A2, and A3. The SSTs in *SmoothAnom* retain the same mean state as the *Reference* experiment but suppress the variability associated with transient mesoscale processes. In contrast, the SST boundary conditions for *SmoothClim* retain the small-scale variability but smooth out the climatological SST gradients associated with sharp ocean fronts, which is evident as differences in the mean state. We note that the small differences in mean SST between *SmoothAnom* and *Reference* are a consequence of the period used for climatology calculations when defining anomalies (1991-2020) and the period plotted (1980-2023). These boundary conditions are thus well-suited to isolate the response of the large-scale atmosphere to extratropical SSTs associated with transient mesoscale features and sharp climatological fronts on atmospheric dynamics.

Figure 2: SST boundary conditions in the Gulf Stream region for *Reference*, *SmoothAnom*, and *SmoothClim* experiments. From top to bottom: (i) daily mean SST for 2020-01-01, (ii) differences in daily mean SST between *SmoothAnom/SmoothClim* and *Reference* experiments, (iii) standard deviation of daily mean anomalies, (iv) daily SST climatologies for January 1st, and (v) differences in daily mean SST climatology between *SmoothAnom/SmoothClim* and *Reference* experiments.

4 Data availability

4.1 ECMWF IFS data

Output variables and frequencies from IFS simulations exactly match the data produced for reference simulations, which is described in detail in EERIE deliverable 9.3. A large fraction of IFS regridded output from idealised simulations is now available on the [Levante](#) and [JASMIN](#) computing platforms. Work is ongoing to archive all idealised IFS data at native resolution to the ECMWF operational Meteorological Archival and Retrieval System ([MARS](#)), where it will be publicly available under a new EERIE data class (“ed”).

4.2 Met Office UM data

The data produced from idealised Met Office simulations is as agreed for the atmospheric part of the EERIE coupled simulations, with some additional high frequency variables produced. Due to resourcing issues, currently this data is primarily only available from the Met Office data archive, with small subsets being provided on JASMIN by request. In due course we plan to standardise the data format (CMORise the data) and make much more of it generally available.

5 Evaluation of idealised experiments

This section provides a preliminary evaluation of the atmospheric response to the direct thermodynamic forcing attributable to mesoscale extratropical SST anomalies associated with transient mesoscale features by comparing the *Reference* and *SmoothAnom* experiments described in section 1.

5.1 Local atmospheric response

5.1.1 Eddy composites in IFS simulations

In EERIE deliverable 9.3 (Roberts, C.D. et al. 2024) it was demonstrated that IFS reference simulations are able to simulate a local atmospheric response to SST anomalies associated with ocean mesoscale eddies. This was shown by creating composites of high-pass filtered atmosphere fields based on observation-based estimates of anticyclonic eddy locations in the Southern Ocean. Such composites provide an estimate of the average impact of ocean eddies on the atmospheric fields of interest. Figure 3 shows equivalent composites calculated for *SmoothAnom* and *Reference* experiments with the IFS Tco1279 (~9 km) atmospheric model. This comparison indicates that our approach to anomaly filtering (Section 3) effectively suppresses the local atmospheric response to transient mesoscale SST anomalies.

Figure 4 shows similar observation- and model-based composites for total precipitation. In this case, the *Reference* and *SmoothClim* experiments both simulate a stronger-than-observed precipitation response to Southern Ocean eddies and this signal is eliminated in the *SmoothAnom* experiments. However, we note that the magnitude of our observation-based precipitation composites is smaller than estimated by some other studies (e.g. Frenger et al. 2013), which likely reflects differences in the data used and compositing methodology, including rotation and rescaling of fields before compositing. The impact of these choices will be investigated in future

work. Nevertheless, from this Lagrangian perspective, our modification of the SST boundary conditions in *SmoothAnom* has a demonstrable impact on local mesoscale air-sea interactions and the variability of the local MABL.

Figure 3: As figure 8 in EERIE deliverable 9.3, but calculated from *Reference* and *SmoothAnom* atmosphere-only simulations with the IFS Tco1279 (~9 km) model. Eddy composite means are derived from 1204617 snapshots of anticyclonic eddies identified from AVISO during 2021 in the Southern Ocean between 25°S and 60°S.

Figure 4: Composite means of high-pass filtered precipitation for observation-based estimates of anticyclonic eddy locations in the Southern Ocean (25°S to 60°S) identified during January-September 2021. Observation-based composites are calculated using data from the GPM-IMERG precipitation product (Huffman et al. 2015, 2020). Model-based composites are calculated for *Reference*, *SmoothAnom* and *SmoothClim* atmosphere-only simulations with the IFS Tco1279 (~9 km). and IFS Tco399 (~28 km). Due to availability of GPM-IMERG only January-September 2021 are used (900981 snapshots of anticyclonic eddies identified from AVISO).

5.1.2 Local SST-wind regressions in Met Office simulations

The spatial scale dependency of thermal (SST and near-surface winds) air-sea coupling has been calculated for the full SST and SmoothAnom simulations, at two resolutions, for the Met Office model. As described in the Month 18 technical report, the high-pass filtered coupling strength (work done in WP5) is strongly enhanced at higher model resolution, likely due to mesoscale processes, and all the EERIE models have coupling strength similar to observations. Given this

result and metric, assessing how the coupling strength is changed when the SSTs are filtered in these SmoothAnom AMIP-style simulations may give further insight.

Figures 5 and 6 show this coupling strength metric, for DJF and JJA seasons respectively, for the Met Office N216 (MM) and N640 (HH) resolution simulations. It is notable that the SmoothAnom experiments have considerably reduced regression values over quite wide regions of the ocean, indicating that removal of the eddy signatures from the SST certainly alters the air-sea interaction processes at the surface. Further analysis will be needed to understand these differences, and to link them to any changes above the atmospheric boundary layer.

Figure 5: Regression of daily, high-pass (3°) filtered SST and near-surface wind speed for DJF for Met Office MM and HH resolution simulations, using full SST (denoted AMIP) and filtered SST (denoted AMIP-SSTeddyfilt) forcing, as well as from observations (CCMP-ESA-CCI). 21 years of data are used for MM and 17 for HH.

Figure 6: As Figure 5 but for JJA.

5.2 Global mean trends

The EERIE atmosphere-only reference simulations accurately capture long-term trends and interannual variability in several key climate metrics, which partly reflects the strong constraint from the specified SST boundary conditions. In figure 7 it is clear that trends and variability in quasi-global mean 2m temperature, TOA radiation, precipitation, and total cloud cover are generally insensitive to the details of the ocean mesoscale in the specified SST boundary conditions. For example, time series of global mean 2m temperature from the IFS Tco399 configuration are effectively indistinguishable in the *Reference*, *SmoothAnom*, and *SmoothClim* experiments. This is not surprising, as the spatial filtering described in Section 3 is designed to preserve the area integral of the prescribed SST boundary condition and thus experiments share the same large-scale SST forcing.

Figure 7: Global mean (or quasi-global mean) time series of 2m temperature, TOA net radiation balance, total precipitation, and total cloud cover in *Reference*, *SmoothAnom*, and *SmoothClim* simulations from IFS Tco399 (~28 km) and Tco1279 (~9 km) configurations. Time series are plotted as annual means and are compared to equivalent data from ERA5 (black), GPM-IMERG (brown), GPCP (pink) and CERES (grey).

5.3 Impact on the atmospheric mean state

As emphasised in Section 3, the only configuration difference between the *SmoothAnom* and *Reference* experiments is the variance of extratropical SST anomalies in the specified boundary conditions. For this reason, any differences in the atmospheric mean state between these experiments must arise from non-linearities in the atmospheric response. For example, Ma et al. (2015) proposed that non-linearities in the relationship between temperature and saturation vapour pressure could result in a net impact on the MABL from the asymmetric response to warm-core vs cold-core eddies.

Figure 8: Differences in seasonal climatologies of zonal mean wind based on single-member *Reference* and *SmoothAnom* experiments with IFS Tco1279 (~9 km) for the period 1985-2023. Grey contours indicate the seasonal climatology of zonal mean zonal winds in the *SmoothAnom* experiment. Statistical significance is estimated using a single sample T-test on the distribution of differences between paired ensemble means. For example, we calculate the difference between ensemble mean JJA seasonal means separately for each year and then calculate p-values for the null hypothesis that the mean of this sample of seasonal mean differences is equal to zero. This test assumes that year-to-year variations in seasonal mean differences are independent. Hatching indicates regions where p-values are less than 0.1.

Figure 8 shows the difference in zonal wind climatologies (1985-2023) from single-member *Reference* and *SmoothAnom* experiments with IFS Tco1279 (~9 km). These experiments indicate that the presence of transient mesoscale SST anomalies in the prescribed boundary conditions seems to have a small (i.e. less than 1 m/s) but systematic impact on the climatological zonal winds. The vertical and latitudinal structure of the zonal wind response varies by season and hemisphere, though the strongest signals tend to be associated with slight poleward shifts in the tropospheric eddy-driven jet. For example, the presence of ocean eddies is associated with positive and negative zonal wind anomalies to the north and south, respectively, of the zonal wind maxima at ~30 °N and ~200 hPa during the DJF, MAM, and JJA seasons (figure 8).

The location, vertical structure, and magnitude of the poleward shifts of the tropospheric jet in IFS Tco1279 experiments are similar to a previously described response in highly idealised experiments (cf. figure 5 of Foussard et al. 2019). Specifically, Foussard et al. (2019) used a zonally-symmetric Northern Hemisphere aquaplanet configuration of WRF with time-invariant SST forcings and found a robust signal of a poleward shift in the storm track and tropospheric jet when

ocean eddies were taken into account. They attributed this change to more intense air-sea interaction and convective heating above ocean eddies, which modified the baroclinicity of the atmosphere leading to a poleward shift in the jet and storm track.

Figure 9: As figure 8, but for differences in seasonal climatologies of zonal mean wind based on 5-member *Reference* and *SmoothAnom* experiments with IFS Tco399 (~28 km).

Interestingly, we do not see the same impact on zonal wind climatologies in the lower-resolution 5-member *Reference* and *SmoothAnom* experiments with IFS Tco399 (figure 9). For example, there is no evidence for a statistically robust poleward shift in the Northern Hemisphere tropospheric jet during JJA in IFS Tco399 experiments. This difference may reflect a genuine resolution sensitivity or could be an artefact of sampling uncertainty.

We also find some preliminary evidence for resolution-dependent impacts of mesoscale SST anomalies on surface climatologies, including 2m temperature (figure 10). For example, Tco1279 experiments indicate that ocean eddies are associated with warming over western North America and cooling over Eurasia. Lower-resolution Tco399 experiments also exhibit evidence for cooling over Eurasia, though the negative anomaly magnitudes are generally weaker and in a different location. In addition, IFS Tco399 experiments do not show the same warming over western North America that is evident in IFS Tco1279 experiments. Again, these differences may reflect resolution sensitivities or they could be a consequence of sampling uncertainties combined with the small effect magnitude.

The results from *SmoothAnom* experiments can be contrasted with those from the *SmoothClim* experiment, which exhibit statistically robust changes to mean 2m temperatures of the oceans. This is expected, as the smoothed SST boundary conditions include a modification of the climatological temperatures. This effect is most obvious in locations with strong SST gradients in the *Reference* experiment, such as the Gulf Stream. Interestingly, these robust changes in temperature gradients over ocean fronts have a very limited impact on the mean state over the continents of the Northern Hemisphere. Further work is required to assess the statistical robustness of these preliminary results and understand the physical mechanisms associated with the large-scale atmospheric response to mesoscale SST anomalies and associated gradients.

Figure 10: Differences in the monthly mean 2m temperature for the period 1980-2023 based on *Reference* and *SmoothAnom* experiments with (top left) single-member IFS Tco1279 (~9 km) and (top right) 5-member IFS Tco399 (~28 km). Bottom left shows the same for the comparison of *Reference* and *SmoothClim* for IFS Tco 399. Hatching shows the regions where the distribution of monthly mean differences is significantly different from zero ($p=0.05$).

5.4 Impact on atmospheric variability

This section describes preliminary investigations into the influence of mesoscale variability and climatological fronts on atmospheric variability. Figures 11 and 12 show the impact of transient mesoscale SST features (i.e. *Reference* minus *SmoothAnom*) on the standard deviation of daily 2 metre temperature (T2m) anomalies in IFS and Met Office simulations, respectively. In both IFS and Met Office simulations, many regions of the sub-tropical and mid-latitude oceans exhibit increased variability of T2m anomalies (figures 11 and 12) when eddies are present in the SST boundary conditions. However, the patterns of change are not uniform within a single model and there are considerable differences across models and between resolutions, particularly over land. For example, there is no consensus between models on the sign of T2m variability change over Europe when comparing *Reference* and *SmoothAnom* experiments (figures 11 and 12).

Figure 11: Differences in the standard deviation of daily mean 2m temperature anomalies for the period 1980-2023 expressed as a percentage based on *Reference* and *SmoothAnom* experiments for Tco1279 (top left), *Reference* and *SmoothAnom* experiments for Tco399 (top right), and *Reference* and *SmoothClim* experiments for Tco399 (bottom left).

Nevertheless, there are some areas where there is an emergent consensus that T2m variability will increase when eddies are present, including over the ocean regions with the highest eddy activity

(e.g. Gulf Stream, Agulhas, Kuroshi) and in subtropical regions along the western coasts of North America, South America, Africa, and in the Arabian Sea. In all cases the changes to near-surface temperature variability are fairly small (relative changes of less than 10%), which is consistent with the small-magnitude local atmospheric imprints based on eddy composites (section 5.1.1). For example, the composite mean T2m signature of anticyclonic eddies in the Southern Ocean have a magnitude of ~30% of the corresponding SST composite (figure 3).

Figure 12: As Figure 11 but for the Met Office model (top MM, bottom HH resolution), over the time periods 1980-2023 (MM) and 1990-2005 (HH), for the comparison of *Reference* and *SmoothAnom* experiments.

Figure 11 also shows the impact of climatological SST fronts (i.e. *Reference* minus *SmoothClim*) on T2m variability in IFS Tco399 experiments. In this comparison, T2m variability is enhanced over

sharp ocean fronts such as the Gulf Stream but otherwise the impacts on variability are rather limited compared to impact of transient mesoscale SST features. These preliminary results are intriguing but require further analysis, including robust estimates of sampling uncertainty and significance, extension to other variables, and the development of causal explanations.

6 Summary and next steps

This report has described a multi-model dataset of idealised atmosphere-only sensitivity experiments, which are designed to complement EERIE reference simulations and help disentangle the impacts of the ocean mesoscale on weather and climate variability. These experiments provide a framework to evaluate the response of the global atmospheric circulation to the *direct* thermodynamic forcing attributable to extratropical SST anomalies associated with quasi-stationary fronts or transient mesoscale features (e.g. nonlinear eddies). These idealised experiments have been conducted with two resolutions of the IFS (~28 km and ~9 km) and HadGEM3 (~60 km and ~20 km) atmosphere models. Other than the specification of SST boundary conditions, the idealised simulations described here are identical to the EERIE atmosphere-only reference experiments described in EERIE Deliverable 9.3 (Roberts, C.D. et al. 2024). A preliminary evaluation of the IFS *SmoothAnom* experiments indicates that transient mesoscale SST anomalies can have a small but systematic impact on the climatological zonal winds and position of the tropospheric jets. However, the vertical and latitudinal structure of the zonal wind response to ocean eddies in these experiments varies by season, hemisphere, and model configuration. Future work will assess the statistical robustness of these preliminary results and work towards understanding the physical mechanisms associated with the large-scale atmospheric response to transient mesoscale SST anomalies and quasi-stationary fronts in the EERIE simulations.

Specific activities to be undertaken in collaboration with EERIE project partners and collaborators include the following:

- Expansion of this preliminary evaluation to include additional experiments (e.g. *SmoothClim*) and other models (e.g. UM experiments described above). We also hope to entrain other groups to run the same experimental protocols with different models to increase the multi-model ensemble.
- A careful evaluation of the statistical robustness of diagnosed impacts, including sensitivities to horizontal resolution and the impact of ensemble size. For example, one could compare differences from higher-resolution experiments (i.e. Member1 vs Member1)

to the distribution of all pairs available in lower-resolution ensemble experiments (i.e. Member1 vs Member1, Member 1 vs Member2, ... etc).

- A more granular evaluation of zonal mean responses (e.g. by ocean basin) and more detailed evaluation of processes (e.g. diagnostics that provide a link between ocean eddies, the MABL, and tropospheric eddy-driven jets).
- Link the analysis of coupling strength ongoing in WP5 to these idealised simulations to gain insight into the role of the eddies in coupling.

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Appendix

Figure A1: As figure 2, but for the Agulhas current region.

Figure A2: As figure 2, but for the Kuroshio current.

Figure A3: As figure 2, but for the global domain.